

RADIANT CREATOR

Workshop

**“Innovative approach
to designing business
models for sustainable
food systems,
supported by artificial
intelligence.”**

Ljubljana, Wednesday, 23. April, 2025

Hosted by Jožef Stefan Institute

Contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction	5
1.1 Background and objectives	5
1.2 Workshop framework and participants	6
2. Presentations	8
2.1 Presentations Overview	8
2.2 Presentations Abstracts	9
3. Demonstration activity - Guided practical session with the MAG system	11
4. Outputs of discussions	13
2.1 Strengths and weaknesses of the system MAG	13
2.2 Potential applications of MAG	15
5. Concluding Remarks	19
Annex I – Program	20

Executive Summary

The CREATOR workshop, held on 23 April 2025 in Ljubljana, Slovenia, was organised as a key step in the validation process of MAG – Market Avenue Generator, an AI-supported Decision Support System (DSS) developed under the Horizon 2020 RADIANT project. MAG is designed to support the development of sustainable business models based on underutilised crops (UCs), addressing critical gaps in strategic planning, sustainability integration, and innovation readiness within the agri-food sector.

The main objective of the workshop was to test the usability, relevance, and potential applications of MAG with a targeted group of stakeholders from Slovenia, including end-users (farmers and entrepreneurs), advisors (consultants and innovation coaches), and representatives of support institutions (such as development agencies, chambers of commerce, and public bodies). The workshop provided a practical, hands-on opportunity to explore the tool, offer feedback, and reflect on its role in business model innovation.

The workshop programme was structured in three core sections:

- Introductory presentations, which contextualised the RADIANT project and introduced the MAG system, including its structure, purpose, and key functionalities.
- A guided practical session, where participants tested MAG individually using sample business ideas and received real-time AI-generated feedback. They explored core modules such as Lean Canvas, TRL assessment, business modelling, sustainability assessment, and insights.
- A validation and discussion component, where participants assessed the strengths and weaknesses of the system and explored its real-world applicability in various professional settings.

Key outcomes of the workshop:

- Positive feedback on MAG's structured workflow, its ability to prompt critical thinking, and the value of AI-driven suggestions for refining business models.
- Particular appreciation for the sustainability module, which was viewed as comprehensive and highly relevant, especially among participants from public or financial institutions.
- Identification of challenges, such as need for clearer onboarding instructions. Some users found the English-only interface a barrier, and others expressed a desire for features to streamline iterative work, such as resolving repeated AI comments.
- Clear recognition of MAG's potential use cases, including in business incubators, advisory services, education, grant applications, and rural entrepreneurship. It was seen as especially beneficial for early-stage innovators lacking structured planning tools or expert support.

The workshop demonstrated that MAG fills a significant gap in current business model development practices by offering a step-by-step, AI-enhanced approach with a strong sustainability focus. The feedback gathered during the event will directly inform the final development phase, contributing to improvements of the tool, before public release in July 2025.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and objectives

In recent years, food systems have faced growing pressure due to climate change, biodiversity loss, environmental degradation, and shifting consumer preferences toward healthier and more sustainable diets. These developments have exposed weaknesses in existing agri-food structures and highlight the need for innovative business models, value chain strategies, and decision-making tools that can support more sustainable, inclusive, and resilient food systems.

The [RADIANT project](#) (Realising Dynamic Value Chains for Underutilised Crops), funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, addresses the urgent need to diversify European agri-food systems by promoting the cultivation and market integration of underutilised crops (UCs). UCs are species that are traditionally cultivated in certain regions but remain marginalised in mainstream agriculture. Despite their agronomic, nutritional, and ecological benefits -including adaptability to local conditions, climate resilience, and contributions to biodiversity- they often lack formal market access and are excluded from dominant value chains. The absence of structured support for business model development, combined with limited tools for sustainability assessment and innovation planning, presents a major bottleneck for entrepreneurs, farmers, and institutions aiming to bring UC-based innovations to market. These challenges are compounded by growing pressures on food systems to transition toward sustainability, climate resilience, and inclusiveness.

To address this gap, the [EcoEnvAI](#) group from [Jožef Stefan Institute](#) has developed [MAG – Market Avenue Generator](#), an AI-supported Decision Support System (DSS) tailored to the needs of the agri-food sector. MAG provides a structured, iterative framework for developing sustainable business models based on underutilised crops (UCs), integrating Lean Canvas methodology, Technology Readiness Level (TRL) assessment, and comprehensive sustainability assessment (economic, environmental, and social). The system supports real-time model creation and refinement through AI-generated feedback and

expert reviews, ensuring alignment with market requirements ([Deliverable 6.3](#)).

The CREATOR workshop was held on 23 April 2025, as part of the MAG system's validation process. The aim was to present the tool to a targeted group of stakeholders, selected to reflect the diversity of actors involved in agri-food business planning. The workshop brought together end-users (such as individuals planning to develop their own agri-food ventures or business ideas), advisors (technical and business consultants), and support institutions (including representatives from public bodies, financial organisations, and development agencies). The workshop provided a practical, hands-on opportunity to test the MAG system, assess its structure and usability, and discuss its potential relevance within different professional contexts. Through guided evaluation and structured discussion, participants offered valuable insights into the system's logic, strengths, and areas for improvement.

1.2 Workshop framework and participants

The workshop took place in Ljubljana, Slovenia, and was held in Slovenian, as the majority of participants were national stakeholders. Although the user interface of the MAG tool was in English, participants did not report any significant language-related difficulties during testing. Although the event was open to international participants, all participants were based in Slovenia, reflecting the local reach and context-specific nature of this CREATOR activity. The workshop programme was divided into three core sections: Plenary presentations session, an interactive session using the MAG tool and guided validation exercises session. This format was chosen to gain practical insights into the user-friendliness of the system and its applicability in practice, while at the same time encouraging participants to take ownership of the development process. In preparation for the event, 145 invitations were sent to relevant Slovenian stakeholders, as well as additional invitations to project partners outside Slovenia. A total of 15 participants took part in the event. All were professionals from Slovenia and reflected the diversity of stakeholders involved in innovative support systems in the agri-food sector. The participants represented the following stakeholder groups (Figure 1):

- End users (47%) – those who could use MAG in developing their own business models;
- Advisors (33%) – technical experts, agricultural advisors and innovation coaches who support others in the sector;
- Support institutions (20%) – public sector representatives, funding institutions, chambers of commerce and regional development centres.

Figure 1. Distribution of workshop participants by stakeholder group.

These specific stakeholder groups were deliberately selected in line with the co-creation approach of the RADIANT project. By including participants from different parts of the value chain, -those who use business models, those who support them and those who influence the environment-, it was ensured that the feedback concerned both practical use and integration at a broader system level. Given the small number of participants and the diversity of stakeholder backgrounds, no formal working groups were formed. Instead, all activities were conducted in a collaborative setting. This ensured a continuous exchange of perspectives and supported the co-creative nature of the validation process.

2. Presentations

The workshop began with three plenary presentations aimed at contextualising the event, introducing the core features of the MAG tool, and fostering a shared understanding of business model challenges in the agri-food sector for UC. Rather than presenting new research findings, these sessions therefore provided the background and rationale for MAG, highlighting how AI can support strategic decision-making for sustainable agri-food value chains.

2.1 Presentations Overview

Table 1. Overview of workshop speakers and topics

Speaker - Institution	Time	Title
dr. Marko Debeljak - IJS	09:15 – 09:30	Purpose and objective to the workshop
Jurij Giacomelli - Meta	09:30 – 10:15	Business planning in the content of the RADIANT project
dr. Tanja Dergan - IJS	10:00– 10:15	Presentation of the MAG system

Figure 2. Presentation on business model planning and investment logic by Jurij Giacomelli (META Group).

2.2 Presentations Abstracts

1. Opening of the workshop – Presented by dr. Marko Debeljak

The first presentation introduced the context of the RADIANT project and the objectives of the CREATOR workshop. He outlined the challenges facing today's agri-food systems - climate change, biodiversity loss, fragmented markets - and emphasised the project's mission to support the integration of underutilised crops into dynamic value chains. The speaker explained how innovative tools such as MAG (Market Avenue Generator) can contribute to building sustainable and resilient business models and presented the structure and expectations for the workshop day.

Dr. Marko Debeljak is a senior researcher at the Jožef Stefan Institute in the Department of Knowledge Technologies. He holds a PhD in forest ecology and has more than 25 years of experience in ecological modelling using artificial intelligence methods. His recent work focuses on AI-supported decision support systems (DSS) for sustainable agriculture and food systems. He is an associate professor and collaborates internationally in EU research projects and academic institutions.

2. Business planning in the context of the RADIANT Project – Presented by mag. Jurij Giacomelli

The second presentation introduced the concept of dynamic value chains (DVCs) and their application to business planning for innovations in the agricultural and food industry. The speaker explained the structure of dual-cycle value chains, separating production and market cycles, and discussed how this approach can help stakeholders define, structure and optimise business strategies for underutilised

crops. The presentation addressed both conceptual and practical elements of innovation-driven planning in the food system and formed the basis for the MAG tool.

Jurij Giacomelli is the founder and Managing Director of Gm, a strategy consultancy specialising in circular transformations and sustainability innovation. He is also an investment manager for META Ingenium, a venture capital fund managed by META Ventures, and serves as the Slovenian ESIL Local Leader. His career includes leadership positions in various industries, including media, insurance, design and banking. Among other things, he was the founding CEO of Gorenje Design Studio, a board member of Prva Group and Communications Director of NLB, the largest bank in Slovenia.

3. MAG system overview and demonstration – Presented by dr. Tanja Dergan

The third presentation provided a detailed overview of the MAG system, an AI-supported decision support system designed to support the development of sustainable business models, particularly in the agri- food sector. The speaker explained the modular structure of the system, including the Lean Canvas, Technology Readiness Level (TRL) assessment, business model creation, sustainability assessment and expert review. She also demonstrated the logic and flow of the system, the user interface and the iterative process of refining business models using MAG's feedback features.

Dr. Tanja Dergan is a research associate at the Jožef Stefan Institute. She holds a PhD from the Biotechnical Faculty at the University of Ljubljana in the field of agri-food economics, where she focussed on sustainability assessment using the DEX method. Her research covers agri-food systems and advanced decision support methods, with a special focus on sustainable public procurement and systemic innovation. Her work is central to the development and testing of the MAG system within the RADIANT project.

3. Demonstration activity - Guided practical session with the MAG system

Following the introductory presentations, participants took part in a structured, individual practical session with the Market Avenue Generator (MAG). Each participant was required to bring their own laptop and was given a unique username and password to access the MAG platform via a secure online portal. This ensured full functionality in one-on-one mode and allowed participants to save their work for later refinement.

The practical session lasted approximately 90 minutes, during which participants worked individually and at their own pace, completing a step-by-step exercise. Each participant received printed material, including an example of a business idea that can be used as a starting point for developing a model within the MAG system. Participants also received an example of a finalised business model to help them understand the expected outcomes and the structure of the tool. The session was designed to take them through the entire MAG workflow, starting with the formulation of a basic business idea and progressing through all the key modules of the system:

- Lean Canvas module: For the initial structuring of their business model idea.
- Technology Readiness Level (TRL) Assessment: To assess the maturity level of the innovation or product.
- Business Model module: To define the operational, financial and strategic elements of the model.
- Sustainability assessment: To assess the environmental, economic and social impact at selected nodes of the value chain.
- Insight's module: To receive AI-based real-time feedback and recommendations for improvement of the developed business model.

Figure 3. Participants working individually during the MAG testing session.

Throughout the session, the MAG development team was present in the room to provide live technical support. This included help with system navigation and understanding how the different modules are connected. MAG's AI real-time feedback feature allowed users to iteratively improve their input, simulating a real-life business model development process. The aim of the session was not only to familiarise users with the technical features of the tool, but also to encourage them to think about how MAG could be used in their own context, be it as farmers, business advisors or representatives of funding institutions.

Participants responded positively to the interactive format and many were able to complete the core business modules. The session also served as valuable preparation for the next section, validation and discussion, in which participants shared their impressions and suggestions for improving the system.

4. Outputs of discussions

The last section of the workshop was dedicated to the validation of the MAG tool and was carried out in two steps. Firstly, the participants assessed the strengths and weaknesses of the system, both individually and in a guided discussion. In the second step, they reflected on current approaches to business model development and identified where and how MAG could be useful in their specific context. These activities provided valuable input for understanding the user experience and the practical relevance of the tool.

2.1 Strengths and weaknesses of the system MAG

During this session, participants focused on critically evaluating the tool, with the aim of gathering user-centred feedback on the strengths and weaknesses of each module. The activity lasted 45 minutes and was divided into two parts:

1. Individual validation (30 minutes)

Each participant received a printed validation form on which they could note the strengths and weaknesses of each MAG module (Figure 4). To assist in reflection, a list of guiding questions was displayed on the wall (Figure 5). These prompts encouraged participants to think about navigation, functionality, decision support and user experience.

Figure 4. Validation forms.

Figure 5. Guiding questions used during the MAG validation session.

2. Sharing and discussion (15 minutes)

After completing the forms, participants were invited to share their main impressions in a short group discussion. Each participant had the opportunity to briefly summarise their observations, allowing common themes and concerns to emerge.

The discussion produced several key findings:

The results of this step showed that the overall structure and purpose of MAG was generally viewed favourably. Participants appreciated the tool's ability to support reflection and encourage structured thinking. Many noted that the step-by-step workflow helped them to organise their ideas and identify aspects of their business model that they might otherwise have overlooked. The system was also found to be intuitive and conceptually clear, particularly in the way it linked the different stages of model development. The sustainability assessment module was particularly praised for its depth and relevance, especially by participants with experience in public administration and finance. In addition, the feedback generated by the AI was highlighted as a helpful feature that encouraged users to rethink and refine their inputs. For

many, this feature added value as it encouraged critical thinking and highlighted areas for improvement that they had not originally considered. Despite these strengths, participants also pointed out areas for improvement. Several users had difficulty navigating the system, particularly when it came to understanding their current position in the workflow and knowing how to get to the next step. Language was also mentioned as an obstacle, as the English-only interface limited some Slovenian-speaking participants in their work. In terms of content, certain sections felt repetitive or disjointed, with some participants reporting that their input did not always transfer logically across modules. Some participants noted confusion regarding the intended user perspective (individual vs. organisation), suggesting the need for clearer introductory instructions. Finally, several users expressed interest in a feature that would allow them to mark comments generated by the AI as “resolved” to reduce redundancy during iterative work.

Some features elicited mixed reactions, depending on users’ background and familiarity with the digital world. For example, while many users appreciated the suggestions generated by the AI and the depth of the sustainability module, others felt overwhelmed by the amount of feedback or unsure how to interpret certain indicators. Although the modular structure was seen as a strength by most, some participants found the transitions between modules unclear or abrupt. These findings highlight the importance of designing the system with flexibility and adaptability in mind to meet the diverse needs of the target group.

The participants showed a high level of engagement and made constructive suggestions aimed at making the system more intuitive, accessible and customisable to the different needs of the users. These findings will be considered in the finalization of the tool, particularly in improving usability and contextualised support.

2.2 Potential applications of MAG

To find out where and how MAG could be used most effectively in practice, the next session of the workshop focused on practical application scenarios. The activity aimed to identify current practises

in business model development and explore how MAG could complement or enhance them. Participants were asked to reflect on their own professional experiences and consider the potential value of MAG in their specific work environment. The session lasted approximately 45 minutes and was divided into two parts:

1. Individual reflection (20 minutes)

Each participant was given sticky notes and asked to reflect on two key questions:

- *What practices are currently used in business model development?*
- *Who could benefit from the application of MAG and in what context?*

To support this process, a set of questions were displayed on the wall to encourage participants to think about common challenges, existing tools or frameworks they use, and gaps in support systems (Figure 6). Participants worked independently and wrote their contributions on sticky notes.

WHERE AND FOR WHOM COULD THE SYSTEM BE USEFUL?

CURRENT PRACTICE

VS

POTENTIAL USE OF MAG

 Time: 45 min

Individual work

Discussion

- How are business ideas or models currently developed in your organisation/farm/company?
- Who is usually responsible for this?
- What methods or tools do you currently use – if any?
- Where do you most often encounter difficulties? (e.g. understanding the market, numbers, connecting ideas into a coherent whole...)
- Do you have access to support (e.g. advisors, programmes, tools)?
- What do you feel is missing?
- ...

- Who in your environment could use this tool? (e.g. farmers, entrepreneurs, cooperatives, advisors...)
- What would be the biggest benefit of this tool for you or your colleagues?
- What would need to change (language, access, support...) for you to realistically start using it?
- Where do you see the greatest potential for using the MAG tool in your sector or professional context?
- What could discourage you (or others) from using such a system?
- If you were to start developing a new business idea today – would you use MAG?
- ...

Figure 6. Guiding questions used during the MAG validation session.

2. Group sharing and open discussion (25 minutes)

Participants posted their reflections on a feedback wall and shared key points with the group (Figure 7). This led to an open discussion in which individual observations were compared, recurring themes identified and collective insights formulated.

Figure 7. Participants' reflections on the feedback wall.

The discussion produced several key findings:

- Most participants confirmed that business model development is often informal, fragmented or using generic tools (e.g., Excel or Word templates) with little structured support.
- The majority do not use specific tools to integrate sustainability or readiness assessments into business planning.
- There was widespread agreement that MAG fills a critical gap, especially for early-stage innovation, by providing a logical sequence and sustainability-orientated assessment that is often lacking in current practise.
- Several participants emphasised that MAG could improve the quality of funding proposals, particularly for grant or investment applications that require sustainability justification or a clear business model logic.

- It was suggested that the tool could be particularly valuable for small-scale producers and rural entrepreneurs who often do not have access to expert advice or structured planning frameworks.
- Some raised the idea that MAG could be integrated into advisory and training programmes, both in the public sector (e.g. regional development services) and in academia (e.g. entrepreneurship and agribusiness courses).
- Several participants pointed out that MAG could serve as a highly effective support tool in business incubators and training programmes, especially for early-stage entrepreneurs who benefit from step-by-step business planning support. The system was also seen as potentially valuable for use in formal business support programmes, public tenders and education.

In conclusion, participants from different sectors - academia, development agencies, chambers of commerce, banks, investment funds and agri-food industry organisations - all recognised high potential for the use of MAG in their own areas. They emphasised that the structured, AI-supported workflow promotes critical thinking and long-term strategic planning. These insights highlight the tool's potential to enhance business support ecosystems and will play a key role in shaping its future positioning, both as a practical instrument for individual users and as a strategic resource for institutions working toward more sustainable agri-food innovation.

5. Concluding Remarks

The CREATOR workshop successfully fulfilled its objective of validating the MAG system in a real, user-centred environment. Through a combination of individual validation and structured discussions, the event not only generated meaningful feedback, but also fostered a sense of ownership among participants from different sectors of the agri-food system. The insights gathered confirmed both the relevance of the MAG approach and the importance of continuing to align its development with the needs of users. Participants made valuable suggestions to improve usability, clarify user pathways and strengthen the system's ability to adapt to different operational contexts. Participants agreed that MAG offers a much-needed tool to support business model development in a structured and sustainability-oriented way, especially where such support is currently lacking.

The workshop demonstrated that stakeholders are not only open to the introduction of innovative tools such as MAG, but are also keen to ensure that they are integrated into existing support systems such as advisory services, funding programmes and education programmes.

As we move towards the public launch of MAG, the feedback from this workshop will be an important input into the final adjustments. The strong commitment and forward-thinking spirit of the participants provides a solid foundation for further collaboration and adoption of the tool across the agri-food ecosystem.

Annex I – Program

CREATOR WORKSHOPE AGENDA

Innovative approach to designing business models for sustainable food systems, supported by artificial intelligence

23 April 2025

🕒 09:00 – 09:15 | Registration and welcome coffee

- Arrival of participants and informal networking

🕒 09:15 – 09:30 | Introduction to the workshop

- Welcome address
- Purpose and objectives of the workshop
- Overview of the program

🕒 09:30 – 10:15 | Presentation of the innovative business model design system MAG

- Business planning in the context of the RADIANT project
- Presentation of the MAG system
 - Business model designed
 - Analysis and recommendations for model optimization
 - Optimized business model

🕒 10:15 – 11:45 | Practical use of the MAG system

- Interactive use of the MAG system with guided steps

🕒 11:45 – 12:15 | Coffee break with light lunch

🕒 12:15 – 13:45 | Critical assessment of the system MAG

- Analysis the strengths and weaknesses of the system MAG
- Applicability of the MAG system

🕒 13:45 – 14:00 | Closing of the day

- Summary of key insights

